

RoleLab

A Tool for Collaborative Design of Roles and Skills Within Interdisciplinary Research Projects

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As scientific research becomes increasingly data-driven and computationally intensive, the demand for sophisticated software tools tailored to the needs of researchers continues to grow. Scientific Software Development (SSD) is a field that seeks to respond to this emergent demand in the broader context of software development. It involves features inherited and transformed by the intersection of scientific research and the domain of Open Source Software. This requires different roles from those in commercial software development, constructing a new division of labor that can better adapt to scientific outcomes¹.

Considering this, within the Epiverse-TRACE LAC initiative² we have developed an instrument for the collaborative design of roles when an emergent field, organization or project needs to craft and define specific lists of roles, skills and tasks for fulfilling a particular endeavor. RoleLab was constructed for the “Collaborative Software Development Ecosystem for Public Health Epiverse-TRACE Summit”³, held in Bogotá, Colombia, between June 26 and July 7, 2023. The results of the applications of this instrument will be included in a forthcoming paper. However, we would like to make this instrument available for SSD and OSS communities and for anyone tasked with defining and understanding roles and skills in an ongoing project without knowing how to start.

For its construction, we reviewed professional networks (such as LinkedIn) and communities of data science, Research Software Engineering, Open Source Software and Software development at large. At the same time, we used ChatGPT as a tool to generate profiles tailored to the particular goals we pursued in the project. Then we adjusted this information for creating a list of roles and skills needed for SSD.

What is this tool recommended for?

For exploring already existing roles and skills in a particular interdisciplinary field or activity, positioning members of a team in the tasks they perform, offering the opportunity to name their roles or for crafting the definition of new ones. It is also useful for exploring people’s expectations about professional growth. Finally, it can be used for understanding the nature of division of labor within a particular community or organization by asking:

- Do people perform a single role within the team?
- If not, does this mean that the team requires a wider -not so strict- division of labor?
- Are roles the same thing as job positions or titles?
- What kind of roles have been selected and crafted? Can they be grouped and classified in different kinds?
- Which roles’ categories connect different expertise and people within the team?

¹ Cf. <https://data.org/news/the-data-ecosystem-designer-designing-the-future-of-responsible-digital-public-goods/>

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³ <https://zenodo.org/records/10932686>

What outcomes can we expect from it?

A dataset with information about roles, the people who perform them, the skills they need for this performance and the skills they want to acquire (needing more attention for further development).

How should it be used?

In-person meetings are required for RoleLab's implementation. For this, we suggest considering four stages.

■ First Stage

Participants should be provided with a printed (A1) version of the tool, presented as a worksheet ⁴. This worksheet contains a table with one list of potential roles and another list of skills that could be needed to perform them. Participants should be instructed to use the worksheet to individually select three roles that best describe the activities they perform within the team. Additionally, they must be encouraged to review the provided definitions and make changes if necessary (consider to provide important questions such as: Do these definitions fully include or represent the activities I conduct to accomplish the selected roles?).

Next, participants should choose some skills from the offered list to add information on the skills that each person currently possesses and those that they consider they need to strengthen or acquire for more effective role performance. Each skill is listed with an ID number, allowing participants to reference the skill in the correspondent roles.

As an additional step, participants could share the results of this activity with other team members. Do they agree with the descriptions of the selected roles? Is there any other information to be added? If this is the case, participants should add it.

⁴ Each worksheet should include a means of identification to facilitate the comparison of gathered information with other demographic or interview-based data of the participant.

Who may be interested in RoleLab?

The instrument can be easily adjusted to different interdisciplinary research projects and teams. However, it has been specially crafted for SSD and Open Source Software communities and projects.

■ Second Stage

We encourage using boards to display the names of different roles throughout the place in which the activity is conducted. By using stickers (representing individuals with their names) and the titles on the boards (representing roles), participants can generate a visual representation of the distribution of the human talent in the list of roles provided, fostering discussion.

■ Third Stage

Participants should gather in groups to contrast their results and discuss guided questions such as:

- What roles does the team(s) currently have?
- What roles are missing and why?
- Is it necessary to think of new roles for strengthening the team(s)?

■ Fourth Stage

Process the information gathered to produce a new, more detailed version of the list. Answer the questions:

- Which roles were discarded?
- What roles have emerged?
- Whose role was under-represented?
- Does the team need to strengthen any skill to better perform their activities?

Suggestions for improving analysis

RoleLab can be perfectly complemented with the use of traditional techniques in quantitative and qualitative research. We particularly suggest the use of any of the following techniques concomitantly:

- Egocentric sociograms asking people to draw the usual roles they collaborate with. Qualification and quantification of connections could be added to the process by using given classifications or scales to weight each relation.
- Interviews or additional workshop sessions to explore results and add more information to the process.

Epiverse-TRACE Summit Report

Citation

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A Role	B Description (This is a generic description to be modified by adding or crossing out words)	C Skills I have	C Skills I need and want to develop/strengthen
Research Software Engineer (RSE)	RSEs are professionals who combine expertise in programming and software development with domain-specific knowledge in a research field. They collaborate with researchers to develop and maintain software tools, frameworks, and platforms used in research projects.		
Data Scientist / Computational Scientist	Data scientists and Computational Scientist are responsible for analysing complex datasets, developing predictive models, and integrating data-driven algorithms into software applications. They leverage statistical modelling, machine learning, and computational techniques to extract valuable insights and optimize software performance. They often work closely with RSEs to implement data processing pipelines and develop data-driven software solutions.		
Domain Expert	A domain expert possesses specialized knowledge in a particular research field. They provide subject matter expertise to the development team, ensuring that the software meets the requirements and challenges specific to the domain. Their insights are crucial for understanding the research objectives and translating them into software features.		
Software Architect	The software architect is responsible for designing the overall structure and architecture of the software system. They collaborate with researchers and RSEs to define the technical direction, select appropriate technologies, and create a scalable and maintainable software design that aligns with research objectives.		
Data Engineer	Data engineers focus on building and maintaining the data infrastructure required for research projects. They develop data pipelines, implement data collection and storage mechanisms, and ensure the efficient handling, processing, and integration of research data. Their work supports data-driven research and facilitates the work of data scientists and researchers.		
Research Coordinator	The research coordinator plays a pivotal role in managing and coordinating research projects. They liaise with researchers, stakeholders, and the development team to ensure effective communication, monitor project progress, facilitate resource allocation, and ensure that research objectives are met.		
Data Manager	Data managers are responsible for data governance, ensuring that research data is properly collected, organized, documented, and stored. They handle issues related to data privacy, security, and compliance. They work closely with RSEs and data engineers to ensure the integrity and accessibility of research data.		
Open Science Advocate	Open science advocates promote and implement practices that foster transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration in research. They work closely with the development team to ensure that research software adheres to open-source principles, promotes data sharing, and enables the dissemination of research findings.		
International Networking expert	International networking experts are responsible for designing, implementing, and maintaining network infrastructure that supports software applications on a global scale. They ensure smooth communication, optimise performance, enhance security, and address network-related issues to enable seamless operation of the software across international teams.		
Research Quality Assurance Tester	Research quality assurance testers are responsible for testing and validating software solutions in a research environment. They design and execute test cases, identify and report bugs or issues, and work with the development team to ensure the quality and reliability of research software applications.		
Research Software Support Specialist	Research software support specialists provide technical assistance and support to researchers using software tools and applications. They troubleshoot issues, provide guidance on software usage, and help researchers optimize their workflow by leveraging software capabilities.		
Technology advocate	A technology advocate is someone who actively promotes and supports the adoption and use of a specific technology, including software, by sharing its benefits, demonstrating its value, and providing guidance to users and developers.		
Training Researcher	Training Researchers are responsible for conducting research and designing training programs to enhance the skills and knowledge of team members and users. They analyse training needs, develop relevant materials, and evaluate the effectiveness of the training initiatives to promote professional growth and improve the overall performance of the team.		
Social science researcher	A Social Science Researcher applies social science principles and methodologies to study user behaviour, preferences, and societal implications related to software applications. They contribute insights, qualitative methods and data-driven perspectives to ensure user-centric and socially responsible software development.		
Community researcher	Community researchers are responsible for gathering user insights and feedback to inform the development and improvement of software applications. They engage with the user community, conduct research, and collaborate with the team to ensure user needs are met, resulting in user-centred software solutions.		
Cloud based technology specialist	A Cloud-Based Technology Specialist are responsible for implementing and managing cloud-based solutions to optimize software applications. They have expertise in cloud platforms and services, ensuring scalability, security, and performance of the applications.		
Research Ethics Reviewer	Individuals who assess research proposals, protocols, and methodologies to ensure that they meet ethical standards and guidelines. They play a critical role in safeguarding the rights and well-being of research participants. Ethics reviewers evaluate the ethical implications of the research, including participant consent procedures, data privacy and confidentiality, potential risks, and benefits. Their expertise and evaluation contribute to the ethical oversight and approval of research projects.		
UX/IX (User Experience / Interaction) Designer	UX/IX Designers are responsible for creating user-friendly and visually appealing interfaces. They conduct research, gather requirements, and design prototypes to ensure an intuitive and satisfying user experience.		
Any other role?			

D
Participant name or ID

Hard Skills and Expertise:

- Statistical Analysis:** Proficiency in statistical analysis is essential for understanding and interpreting public health data. This includes knowledge of statistical software such as R, as well as techniques like hypothesis testing, regression analysis, and survival analysis.
- Data Visualization:** The ability to effectively visualize and communicate data is crucial for conveying insights to stakeholders. Skills in data visualization tools such as Tableau, matplotlib, or ggplot2 can help create compelling visual representations of public health data.
- Epidemiological Methods:** Understanding the fundamental concepts and methods of epidemiology is important for analysing health-related data and drawing valid conclusions. Familiarity with study designs, sampling techniques, and measures of disease frequency and association is essential.
- Data Cleaning and Pre-processing:** Raw data often requires cleaning, integration, and pre-processing before analysis. Skills in data cleaning techniques, handling missing data, data imputation, and data standardization are valuable in ensuring the quality and consistency of public health datasets.
- Deep and Machine Learning knowledge:** The understanding and practical application of principles, techniques, and algorithms in deep learning and machine learning. It involves proficiency in neural networks, optimization algorithms, and statistical learning theory, along with familiarity with popular architectures and algorithms.
- Programming:** Proficiency in programming languages such as R is crucial for data manipulation, analysis, and automation tasks. Strong coding skills enable efficient data processing, algorithm development, and implementation of analytical workflows.
- Knowledge of Public Health Concepts:** A solid understanding of public health principles, terminologies, and concepts is essential for effectively applying data science techniques in this field. This includes familiarity with disease surveillance, health indicators, risk factors, and health disparities.
- Data Ethics and Privacy:** Given the sensitive nature of public health data, knowledge of data ethics, privacy regulations, and best practices for data anonymization and de-identification is critical. Professionals should be aware of the legal and ethical implications of handling and sharing health-related data.
- Training methods:** The ability to select and employ various instructional techniques and approaches to deliver effective training programs and facilitate learning experiences. It involves adapting methods to specific objectives and audience needs while considering different learning styles and utilizing a range of training modalities.
- Qualitative methods:** Analyse and interpret non-numerical data, such as textual or visual information, to uncover patterns, themes, and insights. It involves proficiency in data collection techniques, coding and categorization, thematic analysis, and the ability to derive meaningful conclusions from subjective data.
- Gender perspective:** Recognize and analyse the impact of gender on individuals and societies, integrating this understanding into decision-making processes. It involves identifying and addressing gender biases, stereotypes, and inequalities, and actively promoting gender equality and inclusivity.
- Mathematical modelling:** Constructing mathematical representations to analyse and predict complex systems or phenomena. It includes formulating equations, selecting appropriate techniques, and interpreting model outputs to gain insights and inform decision-making.
- Diseases ecology expertise:** understanding the interactions between organisms, their environment, and disease dynamics. It encompasses analysing factors that contribute to disease transmission and using ecological principles to develop strategies for disease prevention and control.
- Quality analysis:** Examining and evaluating the quality of processes, products, or services to ensure they meet specified standards and requirements. It includes using methodologies, testing techniques, and data analysis to identify areas of improvement and ensure high-quality outcomes.

Soft Skills:

- Communication:** Effective verbal and written communication and knowledge sharing skills are vital for software developers to convey their ideas, discuss requirements, and collaborate with team members, stakeholders, and clients.
- Multidisciplinary work:** The use of knowledge and methods from different disciplines without necessarily integrating them. In multidisciplinary approaches, experts from various fields work independently, bringing their disciplinary perspectives to bear on a common problem. Each discipline operates within its own framework and contributes insights from its specific domain. However, there is typically little or no interaction or integration between the disciplines involved. The focus is on parallel investigations rather than collaborative synthesis.
- Interdisciplinary collaboration:** The integration of knowledge and methodologies from different disciplines to address a specific problem or research question. It acknowledges the value of multiple perspectives and encourages collaboration between experts from various fields. In interdisciplinary work, each discipline retains its own distinct approaches and methods, but they are combined to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the issue at hand. The goal is to foster dialogue, exchange ideas, and create synergies between disciplines.
- Transdisciplinary collaboration:** Integrating not only disciplinary knowledge but also engaging with non-academic stakeholders, such as practitioners, policymakers, and community members. It involves collaborative research efforts that blur the boundaries between academia and society. Transdisciplinary projects seek to bridge the gap between academic knowledge and real-world problems by incorporating different perspectives, values, and forms of expertise. The aim is to generate knowledge and solutions that are contextually relevant and can effectively address complex societal challenges.
- Problem-solving:** Software development often involves complex problem-solving. Team members should possess analytical thinking, logical reasoning, and the ability to break down problems into manageable components to find optimal solutions.
- Adaptability:** The software industry evolves rapidly, with new technologies and methodologies emerging regularly. Developers need to be adaptable and open to change, willing to learn new tools and techniques to stay up to date.
- Attention to detail:** In software development, precision is essential. Paying attention to detail helps in identifying and fixing bugs, ensuring code quality, and maintaining overall product integrity.
- Leadership:** While not everyone on a software development team may have a formal leadership role, leadership skills are valuable at all levels. Developers who can take initiative, guide and motivate others, and provide mentorship contribute to a successful team.
- Networking:** the ability to build and maintain relationships with individuals and groups for the purpose of professional or personal advancement. It involves establishing connections, fostering rapport, and engaging in meaningful interactions with others.
- Teamwork:** the ability to work collaboratively and effectively with others towards a common goal. It involves individuals coming together, pooling their skills, knowledge, and resources, and working in harmony to achieve shared objectives.

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